

An Appraisal of Truth in Tiv Ethics as a Panacea for National Integration in Nigeria

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Abstract

Truth as a moral virtue is a concept cherished by almost all cultures of the world. In the Western world, the search for truth made philosophers down the ages to propound theories on the concept of truth. One of such philosophers is Thales, who set the pace to find out the primary stuff of which all things are made and which explains the continuity in change and the underlying unity in the plurality of things. His views were however challenged by the Greek Sophists. Different philosophers at different stages developed theories such as correspondence, coherent, and pragmatic theories of truth. In Tiv society, it is observed that truth (*mimi*), permeates everything in the people's life, it is *gbaaondo* (God's creation). This moral virtue guide and shapes one's identity in a given society. This paper is an appraisal of truth in Tiv religious ethics as a panacea for national integration in Nigeria. The paper adopts the descriptive and narrative approaches. The data collected were presented using expository method. The findings of the study reveal that Tiv people cherished truth since it forms one's character and brings development in a given society. They therefore make use of *swem*, *kor* and *chia* to establish truth. They also give names to indicate the relevance of truth while their proverbs are very instructive, educative and as well developed the reasoning faculty of a person. The study observed with dismay the contemporary negation of truth to falsehood; which has created room for banditry, terrorism, corruption etc. and therefore calls on the necessary agencies to intervene so as to preserve Tiv cultural values and identity in the face of globalization.

Keywords: Truth, Ethics, National Integration

Introduction

Trust known as "*Mimi*" in Tiv; what is truth? This was a logical question put before Jesus Christ by Pilate in his court. This question was not answered; however, it continues to puzzle most philosophers and scholars over the years. The question has become an imperative to understanding what truth entails. The concept of truth in western world is characterized by different theories. To the correspondence theory, truth is correspondence of proposition to fact; the coherent theory assert truth as the acceptance of any proposition as truth depends on its coherence while to the pragmatist a proposition is true if it works or is useful for practical purpose.¹

In Tiv perspective, the moral obligation of an individual is accompanied with his character. It is this that made J. I. Tseayo to confirm that, religion not only provides the Tiv with a worldview, it constitutes a character for action as well. If this were taken away, the whole basis of life has been removed. For Tiv religion welded experience; history and society into meaningful frame reference.² This shows that the Tiv exhibit their religious values such as respect, peace and harmony, once these values are removed, it threatens the individual welfare as well as the society. Each tribe in Africa has its way of expressing what truth is. It is in this context that the study seeks to examine an appraisal of truth in Tiv religious ethics as a panacea for national integration in Nigeria.

An Overview of Truth: A Cross Cultural Perspective

There are various ways in which the word "truth" is conceived in different cultures. For instance, in the western world, it is preceded that, there is an objective universal truth to be found. Thales set the pace to find out the primary stuff of which all things are made and which explains the continuity in change and the underlying

unity in the plurality of things. The Greek Sophist challenges his view and asserts that “Truth is relative depending on the point of view of individual Everybody sees things from his/her own point of view; what is true for you is true for you and what is true for me is true for me.”³ For the Sophist, there is no objective universal truth, for one cannot know anything with certainty. Plato in his quest for truth conceives that truth is an entity existing outside the mind, an entity in the intelligible world. For him, the mind only discovers and participates in it. Truth therefore is one, eternal and unchanging⁴. Emmanuel Kant views truth as a product of judgment, which the mind makes it applies categories on phenomenon (things as they appear to us).⁵

Among the Igbo of Eastern Nigeria, truth is called *eziokwu*. According to Kingsley, *Ezi* the short form of *ezigbo*, means *good*; *Okwu* means *talk while* the opposite of truth is *ugha*.⁶ In Igbo traditional culture, it is believed that what makes a talk good is not how good it sounds, but the truth in it. To C. G. Osuagwu, *eziokwu* means ‘valid, positive or genuine, while *ugha* (Igbo equivalent to falsehood) means disorder, disarray or chaos. The assertion that ... truth orders while falsehood disorders is incontrovertible.’⁷ For the Igbo’s truth orders the world and its absence brings disorder in the world. In this manner, the people would always say *bughi eziokwu* which means good talk. To this, Emeka infers that, the Igbo also have a maxim that says *eziokwu bu ndu* (truth is life). They hold that truth is authenticity (*ugwu ndu*) thus the phrase *eziokwu bun du* (truth is life) means truth being and truth telling is a test of life and morality.⁸ This clearly shows that they value truth. They do not want to hear lies that sound good but to hear the truth.

Furthermore, O. Ifeanyi posit that, among the Igbo, if you want someone to say the truth, you demand of him or her, *kwue ezi okwu*. That is, the person should say it exactly as he/she knows it, heard it or saw it.⁹ In this context, truth is correspondence between a statement of fact or a concrete thing. To this group of people, truth could be obtained by analyzing what a person says. If the analysis reveals that the statement coheres with a set of accepted facts or beliefs then it is true; otherwise it is false. The Yoruba people of the Southwest Nigeria have long developed a systematic way of thinking and articulating mannerism. This is a useful evidence of the dynamism of the Yoruba culture. Yoruba culture is evident in the beliefs, values, customs, practices, and social behaviours of the people. Truth which is a moral value is placed very high among the essential virtues.

The philosophical tradition of the Yoruba had been so anchored on and entrenched in the concept of character development. The concept of character referred to by Yoruba as *Iwa* is a set of qualities that make somebody distinctively interesting or attractive, especially somebody’s qualities of mind and feelings, somebody’s reputation. The word for truth in Yoruba according to Olukayode is *otito*. It is very common to hear the Yoruba say *bi-iro-nlo-longun-odun, ojo-kan lotito ma-ba* meaning, “If you are telling lies for years, one day it will reveal the truth.” The opposite of truth is *iro*. *Otito* reflects ones values, ethics and morals thus, *iwa* (character) reflects the cultural values, ethics and morals which defines Yoruba as a people¹⁰. *Tio si gba eko* means a person who behaves accordingly; by implication, for one to behave well, it means he has good character which *otito* must be one among.

For the Akan of Ghana, truth is rendered as *nokwara* or *nea ete saa*. Wiredu outlines the various expressions which can be interpreted as conveying a notion of ‘truth’, the two most significant being that of *nokware* and the phrase *nea ete saa*. For Wiredu, *nokware* can be interpreted as equating to “truthfulness.”¹¹ Though the nature of the English translation implies it may harbour the qualities of ‘truth’ it does not constitute ‘truth’ ‘in the cognitive sense. Thus, it can be best understood as ‘truthfulness’ in the sense of “honesty.” The literal translation, on the other hand, offers the definition, “being of one voice.”¹² Wiredu further emphasizes that consensus is regarded as a prized value in the Akan community, which suggests that *nokware* can also be interpreted as a notion of ‘truth’ balanced on a sense of communal agreement¹³. This could be regarded as possessing elements of the Pragmatist theory. In addition to *nokware*, Wiredu states that *nea ete saa* is equal to the English phrase, “it is so” and as such, is used by the Akan as a concept of “truth.”¹⁴

The Concept of Truth in Tiv Worldview

The Tiv are predominately found in Benue State, who speaks *Zwa* Tiv “Tiv language”. Moral value is a serious concern for them since it deals with human conduct. Mbiti posits that morals guide people in doing what is right and good for both their own sake and that of their community. They help people do their duties to society and enjoy certain rights from society. It is morals which have produced the virtue that society appreciates and endeavor to preserve such as friendship, compassion, love, honesty, justice, courage, self-control, helpfulness, bravery etc¹⁵. This implies that human conduct is guided by moral behaviour which helps to distinguish what is right from wrong. This moral virtue guide and shapes one’s identity in a given society. This is why it is common to hear the Tiv say *via ngu aa inja i dedoo* “one has a good character.”

The ethical language in Tiv shows that moral virtue of truth and honesty guides the Tiv traditional behavioural pattern. Akaatenger avers that truth and honesty govern Tiv traditional behaviour pattern. The thought process led to actions that were strictly based on the parameter of *mimi* and *jighjigh* as truth and honesty were uncompromising virtues of the people.¹⁶ The ethical language is embedded in the character hence it is from character that one expresses virtue. The ethical norms are so intertwined in such that one cannot exist in isolation. This is the more reason why the Tiv equate *inja* and *ieren* to be the same. It is often heard *via ngu a eren i dedoo ga!* Or *via ngu a inja i dedoo ga!* “One does not have good behaviour or character.” Honesty according to Dzurgba is a common ethical principle; it is expected in everyday life. In the context of character, an honest person is someone who does not lie or steal. In respect of a statement or answer, an honest person is someone who does not hide the truth or the facts the way the facts really are.¹⁷ For the Tiv honesty refers to *jighjigh* as well as *mimi*.

The Tiv word for truth is *mimi* while the opposite is *aie* “lie or falsehood.” Dzurgba affirms that truth means *mimi* in Tiv language; Truth-telling then means saying something plainly or clearly without hiding the facts or information¹⁸. Dzurgba further elicits that *mimi* represents honesty, truthfulness, trustworthiness, faithfulness and loyalty. These ethical virtues, values or principle were used to evaluate character and behaviour and action.¹⁹ In Tiv society Character beget everything in human conduct, this is why it is common to hear the people say *via ngu a inja i dedoo* “this person have a good character or behaviour.” By and large, for one to have a good character, such person must possess moral virtue and avoid the immoral act. Truth must be involved hence it is one of the cardinal points in measuring one’s capability in a given society. For one to become an ancestor he must possessed the virtue of truth during his life time.

Truth is a fundamental tool to Tiv ethical life, this is express in their maxim that *mimi ye kae ga* (truth does not eat without or most appropriately, truth pays). In one of his songs a Tiv traditional singer Solomon Iornem demonstrate the value of *mimi* (truth) thus; *mimi* is Supreme, *mimi* is more than *ikpagher* (amulets or charm) *mimi* is more than *imborivungu* (ancestral pipe), when one has *mimi* in him even when his death is discussed and concluded by witches and wizard he will be save because of his truth. It is with this that truth-telling must be a social thing recognize, accepted and practiced by the people. Dzurgba again insinuates that truth telling and honesty form the basis for trust and confidence in human relationship and interactions.²⁰ The Tiv always emphasize on *mimi* and when a person is found of lying or telling lies the people would say *or u unden ichor* (one climbs raffia palm tree) or *me loo kwagh sha wura u via ga* “I will not plant my crop on this persons rain”. This is to say such person is a perpetual liar, he/she cannot be trusted in anything. Above all when words are spoken in *mimi*, it therefore means that *mimi* corresponds with the actual fact. One in this way would rightly affirm the correspondence theory which states that truth is the correspondence of a proposition to fact.

In Tiv worldview, *mimi* (truth) is referred to as *gbaaondo*. *Gbaaondo* consist of a verb and a noun; *gba* means to carve while *Aondo* refers to God literally, *gbaaondo* means God’s creation. Tiv worldview is made up of both seen and unseen. Upholding the virtue of truth is one of the cardinal points in Tiv worldview. This is why the Tiv would always say *mimi hembra shagba* (truth is more that nobility), or *mimi ka igya chor I shin mnger* (truth is raffia palm branch dropped in water). A person who does not hold unto truth in Tiv is seen as *or u wan iyuhe* “an envious or jealous man”. This is because, it is only an envious man that does not say the truth. *Gbaaondo* is the nature and manner in which thing are or appear in themselves in the natural order. This is why it is difficult

to separate the physical world from the non-physical in Tiv worldview. Truth is viewed in Tiv thought system as that which correspond to the observable harmony of the cosmos at a particular moment. Truth is that which serves to preserve the balance of the macro and the microcosm. It is that which upholds the equanimity of the totality, which produces the greatest good and as such is true to the structure of the world²¹. This shows the natural view of truth among the Tiv; for this group of people, *ieren i sha gbaaondo* “doing things in the natural way” is the unifying force that binds them, when one deviate from it the Tiv would say *tar vihi*.

It is believed that when a person adheres to truth it brings development to the individual and the society at large. The words of a dying mother (Tagude) to her son as contain in *Adan Wade Kohol Ga* buttress this point;

My son” she said, “I know you are but a child but listen carefully to my words and hold onto them. Let them be the legacy I am leaving for you. Allow them to guide your every step in life. Tagude went on: “the kind of legacy your father left for you was that of the forebears. The inheritance I leave for you is in the form of words. Beyond this I have nothing to leave for you.”²²

Tagude continued:

The wise and kind person has seven principles that guide his life and actions: following the path of truth, exhibiting good behavior, patience, commitment, determination, forgiving others of their wrong doings and humility. She further that truth and exemplary behavior are roots in the life of the good and wise man. The personality, to whom truth has value, becomes even wiser as he pursue the course of truth²³.

Truth exhorts everything and when one holds unto it, it is the only virtue that can set one free even in the presence of his enemies.

Another aspect of Tiv worldview related to truth is *swem*; *swem* is a symbol of truth and justice, it is both Spiritual and Corporal and its spirituality binds the people by truth, equality, honesty, sincerity and justice; *Swem* make truth known whenever it is invoked²⁴. In order to obtain truth and justice, *Swem* is being sworn upon to prove one’s innocence among his kinsmen. This is why *Swem* is found in all customary court in Tivland. The significant nature of *swem* made people to name their children equating to *swem*. As a symbol of justice and truth, Suemo Chia’s words capture this analogy “Our way of life with its penchant for truth and fair play is symbolised by the *Swem*, which our ancestors handed down to us. The *Swem* is also a symbol of our oneness, love for truth and fair play, was created out of ashes derived from the burnt skull of Takuruku, our first forebear.”²⁵ Gbenda corroborates this view when he stated that, in Tiv traditional religious culture, truthfulness and justice are cherished by the people. A symbol of *mimi* (truthfulness) and uprightness is called *Swem*²⁶. This clearly shows that *Swem* is a symbol of truth and justice which bind the people in unity. It is on this ground that when someone swears falsely by *Swem*, he/she eventually dies.

Another area of Tiv worldview that emphasizes on truth is *Kor and chia* (Sass wood ordeal). *Kor* was used in ancient Tivland to elicit truth when an offence or crime was committed. When calamity befall one and in order to know the truth, the elders administered *kor* substance. It is in this manner that each and every one *ta chia* (swore) stating his/her case. To this, the Tiv would say, *kor lun kea to* ((truth is in the ear). According to Torkula:

Sasswood is a form of legal procedure to determine the guilt or the innocence of a person in Africa and also in Tiv culture. This legal system is used till today. A similar practice is found among the Ashanti of modern Ghana. In this case, defendant in a trial must drink a locally brewed poison. If he vomits, he is construed to be innocent. If he does not vomit, he dies, providing his guilt. Many African tribes of Bantu origin used this legal process to administer justice in their societies the Tiv inclusive.²⁷

Though *kor* is not 100 percent as *Swem*, this is because it could kill an innocent person whom *ityo* ganged up against or have pointed accusing finger at such a person. Again, Wade role in *Adan Wade Kohol Ga* buttresses this point:

Wade was the last to go for his own calabash of *kor*. Controversy still raged within him as to his innocence or guilt concerning the death of Abum, his brother. When he received his calabash of

the *kor*, he faced his kinsmen and swore: you, my clansmen! If I have killed my brother, Abum, this *kor* I am about to drink should kill me for my guilt. If otherwise, however, this *kor* I am about to drink will kill me because you have so connived.²⁸

Wade's kinsmen were against him because of the legacy of *imborivungu* (ancestral pipe) his father left for him and therefore wanted him dead. That is why Wade *ta chia* taking his position of guilty or not the *kor* should kill him. Chia (justification) is a moral principle among the Tiv people; it is a principle that determines the behaviour of ordinary mortals as well as *mbatsav*.

Naming is a special area in Tiv worldview that stresses the need for truth; names in ancient Tiv society were given based on the events that took place. For instance, the Tiv of *mbayiase* (ancient Tiv days) would give names like Tsavbee (witchcraft has finished), Tsavhembra (witchcraft is great), *imborivungu* (ancestral pipe), Tyongi (there are kinsmen), Tyowase (help of kinsmen), Tyohembra (kinsmen are great) etc. based on the situation or reality on ground. For example, if a wizard who was fond of killing people died, and a child was born within such period, the family would name him Tsavbee signifying that witchcraft is over. As truth is an important virtue the Tiv name their children equating to it. Names like *Mimi* (truth), Ngumimi (she is honest or truthful), *Or-mimi* (person of truth or honest), *Mimidoo* (truth or honest is good), *Mimisen* (truth or honesty descend) etc. signifies that the people adhere to truth.

Proverbs in Tiv worldview is another area of interest because, the moral lessons derived from proverbs enriches character building. It is in line with this that Dzugba and Usue emphasizes that:

Proverbs are expressed facts, ideas or principles that contain varieties of meanings; implication, interpretation or lessons for individual, marriages, couples, families, communication, or ethnic groups. Proverbs are short, exact, precise and decisive statement that shows characteristics of prowess, acumen and agility in human abilities of knowing, thinking, reasoning, and understanding, deciding, choosing, and exercising freewill.²⁹

It therefore means that proverbs do not only provide a desired meaning to the people but also serve as moral instruction and those who stick to it grow in wisdom. Gbenda in the same manner, pointed out that proverbs are used not only for religious, intellectual exercise, and trustworthy witnesses to the social, political and economic ideas of the Tiv people. A child's reasoning faculty and creativity is developed with the use of proverbs.³⁰ Tiv have different kinds of proverbs that depict the concept of truth; these includes *mimi hembra tungu* (truth or honesty is better than collateral), *mimi hembra nyaregh* (truth or honesty is better than riches), *mimi hembra imborivungu* (truth is more than ancestral pipe), *Mimi yua hembra megh* (truth is bitter than poison), *mimi ka mule* (truth is like shadow) *mimi saan ga* (truth cannot be forgotten or lost). All these proverbs point to the fact that truth (*mimi*) is a serious moral virtue that guide the socio-political life of the society.

An Evaluation of Truth in Tiv Religious Ethics as a Panacea for National Integration

The contemporary Tiv society and Nigeria at large is facing a lot of challenges; most of the cherished cultural values are fast eroding and going into extinction. Today, politics has become the order of the day with Christianity as the modern religion. Most Tiv/Nigerian politicians have abandoned truth, the Tiv philosophy of *ya na angbian* has been relegated to the background, hence the winner takes all. The pre-colonial Tiv society built its culture on a sound footing such that *mimi* permeated over everything. It is in respect to this that *swem*, *kor/chia*, proverbs as well as naming of children were upheld in high esteem. For instance, for moral justice, *swem* was sworn upon to prove one's innocence, it was also used for oath taking. While *kor* substance was powerful in such that when one was guilty, he would not vomit the *kor* substance and in the process die. Proverbs were very educative and instructive, since the people would say *or hembe ityo ga* (no one is above *elders*). Therefore, if truth is reappraised and revalidated through these moral virtues, it will create a sustainable development as well as national integration.

Truth is a sacred virtue which when harnessed, it brings unity, harmony, good governance, rule of law, equality and development. The scriptures also acknowledge the importance of truth that "and ye shall know the

truth, and the truth shall make you free” (John 8:32). In a similar vein, the motto of the *Guardian Newspaper* in Nigeria states “Conscience nurtured by truth”. When the virtue of truth as practice by the Tiv people is imbibe at the national level, it will empower inter-ethnic inter-religious and interpersonal cohesion and unity that will strengthen national integration. For truth is not compromise, it centres at what is right and transparent. The absent of truth in the contemporary society creates vacuum for political god-fatherism which leads to corruption, thuggery, terrorism, banditry, herdsmen/farmers crises among others. It also paves way to a society where human life is no more valued. All these forces contribute to disunity and conflict in the country. Nigeria stands a good chance to re-trace their step by imbibing the moral virtue of truth which will change their narrative and enhances national integration.

Conclusion

The work elicits the concept of truth in Tiv religious ethics examining how the word truth is used and applied. A cross cultural analysis of the term was taken from different cultural groups in Africa as well its western world. The work observes that Tiv ethical norms regulate the relationship between the individual and the social groups. The application of truth brings development in all areas of human endeavour. It is worthwhile to conclude using Abeghe Tyu’s words who demonstrate how the ancient Tiv egalitarian society where truth was upheld: “In the days when the Tiv society was intact, a Tiv man on seeing his brother fighting with another tribes-man would not look for the cause of the trouble before joining his Tiv brother in the fighting against the other tribes-man. “*Angbian gbe ga*” brother never disappoints was the saying.”³¹

Recommendations

The future of Tiv religious ethics is at stake due to the dynamic changes in contemporary Tiv society. Traditional institutions that stand at the helm of affairs to curtail the ugly menace that is befalling the society have sold themselves to politicians. Traditional rulers who are supposed to uphold traditional customs and values and pass to the next generation turn to become political thugs. They abandon their traditional practices and embrace other religions such as Christianity where chapels are built in there palace instead of shrines. This have serious effect on the Tiv concept of truth and as well the cherish proverbs which preserve the society are no more taught. Swem which is the symbol of truth and justice have been abandon seeing it as pagan rites. Names which in ancient Tiv society gave meaning to a particular event or purpose, have now changed to English/exotic names. For instance, when a person bears a name which is not English in nature he/she is looked upon as a person in the past.

In order to uphold truth and preserve our traditional values, for national integration, all hands must be on desk. Political stakeholders should join in the race in restoring the decaying cultural values as well as traditional rulers. Politicians should stop enticing traditional rulers with money to influence them. Traditional rulers/elders should resist being influence to compromise their integrity. They should desist from partisan politics and sees themselves as father that accommodate all into onefold. This will enable them to easily promote their cultural values for national integration. They should also endeavour to amplify certain cultural heritage that will assist in achieving the value of integrity and good democracy in Nigeria.

The role of educationalist cannot be overemphasized hence the whole world is becoming a global village and they play a key role in human development. They will impact their knowledge to students and make them to understand the efficacy of abandoning one’s culture hence the Tiv proverb says “*gbenda lihe zan zan kpa aa he ya*” “no matter how long a road is, it leads to a home.” More importantly, parent should teach their children Tiv language and their cultural values and Tiv language should be taught in all institutions of learning in Benue state. Above all, the Tiv concept of truth should be reappraised and revalidated, in order to redirect the society and create atmosphere for sustainable, progressive and transparent democracy in Nigeria.

Endnotes

- ¹T. U. Nwala, *Modern Introduction to Philosophy and Logic*. (Nsukka: Niger Books and Publishing Company, 1997), 40-42.
- ²J. I. Tseyayo, *Conflict and Incorporation in Nigeria the Integration of the Tiv* in E. T. Atel, *Dynamics of Tiv Religion and Culture: A Philosophical-Theological Perspectives*. (Lagos: Free Enterprise Publishers, 2004), 25.
- ³J. Omoregbe Joseph, *Epistemology: A Systematic and Historical Study* (Lagos: Joja Educational Research and Publishers, 1998), 82.
- ⁴W. L. Reese, *Dictionary of Philosophy and Religion: Eastern and Western Thought*. (England: Humanities Press, 1980), 588-559.
- ⁶J. Omoregbe, *Knowing Philosophy: A General Introduction* (Lagos: Joja Educational Research and Publishers, 1990), 42.
- ⁷K. Chukwuemeka, 55, Public Servant, the interview took place on 17/02/2022 at High level Makurdi.
- ⁸C. G. Osuagwa, *Truth and Chaos: Dynamics of Truth within Igbo Cosmology*. (Owerri: African World Communication, 2003), v.
- ¹⁰C. Emeka 58, Businessman, the interview took place on 26/06/2022 at Wurukum, Makurdi.
- ¹¹O. Ifeanyi, 60, Businessman, the interview took place on 24/04/2022 at North bank, Makurdi.
- ¹²A. Olukayode, 50, Public Servant, Divisional Police officer B Division Makurdi, the interview took place in his office on 26/06/2022 at B Division HIGH level Makurdi
- ¹³K. Wiredu, 'The Concept of Truth in the Akan Language' In Coetzee, P. H. & Roux, A. P. J. (eds.) *The African Philosophy Reader*, Routledge, 1998, 234.
- ¹⁴Ibid.
- ¹⁵Ibid.
- ¹⁶Ibid.
- ¹⁷J. S. Mbiti, *Introduction to African Religion* (2ed). (Oxford: Heinemann Educational Publishers, 1991), 174.
- ¹⁸Akaatenger, Anthony-Maria. *Witchcraft, Magic and Sorcery in African Religious Worldview: A Pastoral Reflection on Tiv Religious Tradition* (Makurdi: Phalanx Books, 2015), 50.
- ¹⁹A. Dzugba, *Element of Tiv Culture: Material and Ideological Studies* (Ibadan: John Archers Publishers Ltd, 2016), 38.
- ²⁰Ibid., 38
- ²¹A. Dzugba, *Wanagenian Ethics* (Ibadan: (John Archers Publishers Ltd, 2014), 53.
- ²²A. Dzugba, *Contemporary Ethics: Theory and Issue* (Ibadan: John Archers Publishers, 2007), 66
- ²³Martin Anshi, Wang. *Ieren: An Introduction to Tiv Philosophy* (Makurdi: Obeta Publishers, 2004), 17.
- ²⁴Suemo, Chia. *The Story of Adan Wade: A Tiv Classical* (Trans) Tyozuah Akosu. (Makurdi: Aboki Publishers, 2011), 49.
- ²⁵Ibid., 50.
- ²⁶M. K. Sati, "A Metaphysical Appraisal of Tiv Conception of Reality," A Project in the Department of Religion and Philosophy, BSU Makurdi, Feb, 2010.
- ²⁷Suemo, 239.
- ²⁸S. J. Gbenda, *Eschatology in Tiv Traditional Religious Culture: An Interpretative Enquiry* (Nsukka: Chuka Educational Publishers, 2005), 178.
- ²⁹A. A. Torkula, *The Cosmology in Tiv Worldview*. (Makurdi: Oracle Business, 2006), 29 Print.
- ³⁰Suemo, 25.
- ³¹A. Dzugba, and E. O. Usue, *The Proverbs of the Tiv of Central Nigeria* (Ibadan: John Archers Publishers, 2017), 9.
- ³²S. J. Gbenda, *Eschatology in Tiv Traditional Religious Culture: An Interpretative Enquiry* (Nsukka: Chuka Educational Publishers, 2005), 140.
- ³³T. Abegha, *The Tiv and Tiv Riot* in S. J. Gbenda, *Eschatology in Tiv Traditional Religious Culture: An Interpretative Enquiry* (Nsukka: Chuka Educational Publishers, 2005), 140.